

Impact of Polymeric Hole Selective Layers on Chemical Inductance in Inverted Perovskite Solar Cells

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Abstract

An essential role is played by the charge selective layers, in particular, the hole transport layer (HTL) in determining the performance of perovskite solar cells (PSCs). HTLs contribution is even more substantial in the inverted PSCs (p-i-n) as it also affects the crystallization process of the overlayer perovskite deposition. We probed the influence of HTL on inverted PSCs and quantify the role through admittance spectroscopy, and established the photovoltaic performance correlation with the microstructure of the perovskite. By measuring the low-frequency impedance responses of inverted PSCs, we quantify the photo-induced charge transfer dynamics in the PSCs, revealing negative chemical inductor features at low frequencies in the Nyquist plots. The noted additional recombination pathways are attributed to the ionic vacancies in the interfacial states. The PSCs fabricated with PTAA showed a higher open-circuit voltage, lower recombination, and higher charge carrier lifetime. We supported the chemical inductance behavior through variable temperature frequency-dependent capacitance measurements.

Keywords: Perovskite solar cell, hole transport layers, Charge recombination, Chemical Inductance

1. Introduction

The advancement of perovskite solar cells (PSCs) stands out in the emerging photovoltaic (PV) technologies, attributed to the unique combination of low cost, solution processability, and energy level tuning of the perovskites.¹⁻⁴ The power conversion efficiency (PCE) has been improved to 25.7% for PSCs, through the development of active layer formulation, device interface engineering, and thickness optimization.⁵⁻⁸ Although the n-i-p architect recorded the highest PCE, it also requires high-temperature processing (>450 °C) to prepare the charge transport layer (TiO₂), a methodology not suitable for the manufacturing of flexible devices.^{9,10} Comparatively, p-i-n or inverted planar PSCs can be processed at low temperatures (<100 °C), which makes them suitable for mass production applications including roll-to-roll printing like newspaper and doctor blading.¹¹ Besides the high performance, long-term stability and also the reduction of hysteresis are remaining challenges in PSCs. The possible reasons for hysteresis in PSCs are charge accumulation at interfaces, unbalanced charge carrier transport and extraction, ion and vacancy migration, and trap-assisted charge recombination.¹²⁻¹⁴ Moreover, the presence of defects or traps at the perovskite/charge transport layer interfaces acts as a trapping center for charge carriers, which successively causes non-radiative losses and reduces the lifetime of free-charge carriers, resulting in deterioration of device performance.¹⁵ Such issues can be addressed by developing stable perovskite materials, charge transport layers, and optimized processing conditions.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ The charge selective contacts including hole transport layers (HTLs) and electron transport layers (ETLs) are indispensable components for achieving high performance and stability. They play pivotal roles in extracting and collecting the photo-generated charge from the perovskite to the respective electrode, thus effectively reducing undesirable recombination losses at the interface and improving PV performance. Thus, in particular, the influence of the HTL interface between the perovskite absorber and anode

should not be underestimated, which influences the energy level alignment, growth of perovskite crystals, and charge extraction ability.^{19,20} It is imperative to develop and understand the ideal HTL for fabricating high-performance PSCs. Small perturbation frequency domain techniques, especially electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), offer access to a detailed investigation and understanding of the physical characteristics of PV devices. Over the past years, EIS has revealed several eccentric behaviors including giant photo-induced low-frequency (LF) capacitance, inductive loop at mid-frequencies, and negative capacitance, however, the origin of these phenomena has still not been conclusively understood.²¹⁻²³ Studies have been devoted to a deeper understanding of these prevailing features, which play important roles in the improvement of the PSCs performance.²⁴⁻²⁷ The low-frequency negative capacitance and its correlation to slow transients in the injection current have been studied.²⁸ We also reported that the low-frequency negative capacitance feature in n-i-p type PSCs is intimately related to the interfacial interactions of migrating ions with metallic contact and redistribution occurring at the perovskite interfaces.²⁹ The negative capacitance feature is not limited to the n-i-p type PSCs only but has been also observed in p-i-n based architectures. However, the surface recombination at the perovskite/HTL interface has received less academic interest in the p-i-n type PSCs and how the choice of HTLs affects the device performance has not been comprehensively unraveled.³⁰ In this work, we thoroughly investigated the impact of HTLs in inverted PSCs and quantify the mechanistic insights. We noted that PSCs with undoped PTAA gave PCE of 17.84% with negligible hysteresis, outperforming PSCs based on PEDOT:PSS (14.07%) and undoped P3HT (15.20%) as HTL. To note here, all the HTLs are used as such i.e. without any doping or additives. Interfacial charge kinetics of PSCs was investigated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and thermal admittance spectroscopy (TAS). The presence of the low-frequency chemical inductor feature was noted under the condition of the applied voltage or at different

temperatures. We established an evident relation between the open-circuit voltage and the recombination losses in the PSCs.

2. Results and discussion

The molecular structures of the polymeric HTLs used in this work are shown in Figure 1a-c. The UV-Visible absorption spectra of perovskite films deposited on HTLs are illustrated (Figure 1d), and the triple cation perovskites (CsFAMA) film displays broad optical absorption over the entire visible range with an absorption edge at ~ 785 nm. The CsFAMA deposited on different HTLs display similar optical characteristics, however, the absorption edge is marginally red-shifted. The minute enhancement in the absorption near the bandgap edge of the perovskite formed on the HTL can be attributed to the improved crystallinity of the perovskite attained.³¹ In addition, the PTAA film displayed a higher transmittance in the visible region than those of PEDOT:PSS and P3HT films (Figure S1).

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the perovskite films deposited on different HTLs are depicted (Figure 1e), and the main diffraction peaks appear at around 14.2° , 20.2° , 31.9° , and 40.7° , assigned to the (101), (012), (211), and (024) planes of the CsFAMA crystalline structure, respectively. However, we noted a slight increase in the intensity of the diffraction peaks suggesting the improvement of the perovskite crystallization.

Figure 1: Molecular structures of the HTMs (a) PEDOT:PSS, (b) P3HT, and (c) PTAA, (d) UV-Vis absorption spectra and (e) XRD patterns of the perovskite on different HTLs.

Contact Angle Goniometer measurements (Figure S2) exhibit higher hydrophobicity for both P3HT and PTAA, suggesting reduced wetting of the precursor solutions and affect the morphology of the perovskite films. We recorded the microstructure by capturing the top-view with the help of a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Figure S3), and noted that perovskite film deposited over PTAA shows higher film formation quality and smoother surface comparatively. The improved quality of perovskite attained on top of PTAA is attributed to its surface wettability properties, which favor the crystallization process and reduce the defects in the bulk of perovskite.³² This impacts the device efficiency and charge transportability. The higher (bright) contrasts on the surface are ascribed to the unreacted PbI_2 that is present on the perovskites.³³

To evaluate the influence of the HTLs on PV performance, we fabricated inverted PSCs with a device configuration of FTO/HTL/CsFAMA/6,6-phenyl- C_{61} -butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM)/bathocuproine (BCP)/Ag. The HTL was selected from PEDOT:PSS, P3HT, and PTAA, and the current density-voltage (J - V) characteristics are shown (Figure 2b), and the relevant PV parameters are summarized (Table 1). We noted the choice of HTL significantly affects PSCs performance. The PSC with PTAA measured a PCE of 17.84% along with J_{sc} of 22.98 mA cm^{-2} , V_{oc} of 1064.48 mV, and FF of 72.94%, which was higher than its counterparts with PCEs of 14.07% for PEDOT:PSS based PSC and 15.20% for P3HT, respectively. To note here PEDOT:PSS, based PSC gave a V_{oc} value of 919 mV. The superior PV performance measured for PTAA based PSCs is due to its higher hole selectivity, favorable energetic alignment, and thus lower energetic barrier. The carrier mobility of the P3HT and PTAA is higher than that of PEDOT:PSS which will be beneficial for hole transportation.³⁴⁻³⁶ The energy offsets (Figure 2a) between the valance band maximum of the CsFAMA and the HOMO levels of the HTLs were 0.6 for the PTAA, P3HT, and 0.7 eV for PEDOT:PSS, and this follows the V_{oc} trend. This indicates that energy loss for hole extraction is lowest at PTAA/perovskite

interface. On the other hand, the higher energy offset between the conduction band minimum of CsFAMA and the LUMO level of the PTAA compared to the other HTLs will provide higher electron blocking properties from the perovskite, successively good hole-selectivity of the PTAA, and advantageous to prevent charge recombination at the interface. Moreover, the external quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements display a higher spectral response over the entire absorption range of 400-800 nm (Figure 2d) for the PTAA based PSCs. The integrated J_{sc} values derived from the EQE spectra are 21.04, 20.05, and 21.69 mA cm⁻² for the PSCs with PEDOT:PSS, P3HT, and PTAA, respectively, which are close to that extracted from $J-V$ measurements. We attribute this marginal difference to the differences in the light sources used, which are single wavelengths and lower in intensity than the solar light simulator system.³⁷ In addition, the illuminated area (active device area) is also much lower in the EQE measurement compared with that of the $J-V$ analysis.

Table 1: Photovoltaic parameters of the PSCs with different HTLs.

HTL	Scan	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} (mAcm ⁻²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)
PEDOT:PSS	RS	919.99	22.03	69.41	14.07
	FS	921.63	21.78	67.21	13.49
P3HT	RS	1037.05	21.80	67.22	15.20
	FS	1036.30	21.75	63.46	14.30
PTAA	RS	1064.48	22.98	72.94	17.84
	FS	1063.27	22.78	71.74	17.38

Figure 2: (a) Energy level alignment of at the HTM/perovskite interface, (b) J - V curves of the device with different HTMs in reverse scan under simulated AM 1.5G illumination, and (c) corresponding IPCE and integrated current density.

The forward and reverse scanning J - V curves of the devices (Figure S4) are recorded, and the hysteresis index (HI) is calculated based on the following formula.^{4,38}

$$HI = \left[\frac{J_{RS(0.8 v_{oc})} - J_{FS(0.8 v_{oc})}}{J_{RS(0.8 v_{oc})}} \right]$$

Where $J_{RS(0.8 v_{oc})}$ and $J_{FS(0.8 v_{oc})}$ represent the J_{sc} at 80% of v_{oc} of the reverse and forward scan, respectively. The obtained HI values for the PSCs with PEDOT:PSS, P3HT, and PTAA as HTL are 0.041, 0.059, and 0.025, respectively. Smoothing the surface and the uniformity induces minimum defect states and trap density, resulting in minimizing the hysteresis and providing efficient charge transport.^{39,40} The low value of HI of 0.025 suggests the quality of perovskite, which in turn will suppress the defects (low ion migration, and charge recombination).

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is a conducive and broadly employed tool to study the charge dynamics through the interfaces of PSCs.⁴¹⁻⁴⁵ Nyquist plots (Figure 3) show the PSCs with thee different HTLs measured under dark conditions at different applied voltages in the frequency range from 10 mHz to 1 MHz. The Nyquist plots display only one semicircle. Besides, a small region of the chemical inductor that looks like a negative capacitance arc can also be observed in the low-frequencies range. Such features in the Nyquist plots have been reported for a variety of PSCs,⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ however, its physical origin remains completely unclear.

Arguably, the resistance at low frequency is mainly associated with charge recombination, whereas charge transfer contact responses for the resistance are at high-frequency. The equivalent electrical circuit consists of series resistance (R_s), a charge recombination resistance (R_{rec}), and an inductor element (L) used to fit the small negative arc in the low-frequency region (Figure S5). The extracted parameters from the EIS fitting for the inverted PSCs, using the EC-Lab software, are deduced (Tables S1a-c). We noted that the difference in high-frequency resistance between various PSCs is negligible. Usually, the large radius of the semicircle indicates a higher recombination resistance. From the fitting results, at various bias voltages, the PTAA based PSCs showed a higher R_{rec} value than PEDOT:PSS or P3HT. The higher recombination resistance in the PTAA-based PSCs suggests that PTAA is effective to suppress charge recombination and mitigating charge annihilation at the perovskite/HTL interface, thus benefiting longer lifetimes for charge carrier transport,^{49,50} This result is consistent with the PV properties for PTAA based PSCs. The orientation of molecules is fundamental to the device's performance, and therefore, the perpendicular order of lead and iodine atoms to the PTAA surface can facilitate the nucleation at the perovskite interfaces and will allow effective extraction of charge carriers and lower charge recombination.¹⁴ Additionally, the high hole mobility and electrical conductivity of PTAA will enable high recombination resistance through the fluent transport of the photo-generated charge carriers toward the anode.^{51,52} We noted that the R_{rec} of the PSCs reduces with an increase in applied dc voltage (Figure 4a). This can be attributed to the surface interactions with the accumulated ions/vacancies at the perovskite interfaces resulting in the dominant low-frequencies PSCs response and thus displaying a chemical inductor feature, which mainly appears as a negative value in the axis.^{53,54} The inductive effect is associated with the presence of mobile ions that can have imperative effects on the PSCs. It can be explained by a kinetic model, in which an internal surface voltage that is slowed down by ionic motion relaxes to the quasi-equilibrium state

imposed by the external voltage applied to the PSCs, and this generates a sluggish surface recombination current. We noted the inductive behavior display low features for PTAA based PSC, and arguably the negative chemical inductor behavior can be ascribed to the enhanced recombination. Recently it has been shown that the negative capacitance and hysteresis features in PSCs are ascribed to a similar physical origin, i.e., large kinetic relaxation times because of an increased recombination rate.⁵⁵

Figure 3: Nyquist plots of the inverted PSCs, (a) with PEDOT:PSS, (b) with P3HT, and (c) with PTAA measured under dark conditions with varied applied voltages.

The electron lifetime (τ) of the PSCs is calculated via an equation: $\tau = \frac{1}{2\pi f_{max}}$, while f_{max} derived from the Bode EIS spectra (Figure S6). Subsequently, the PSCs based on the PTAA showed a longer charge lifetime (1.01 μ s) compared to PEDOT:PSS (0.47 μ s) and P3HT (0.77 μ s). Moreover, (Figure 4b), the τ of the PTAA based PSCs is higher at various bias voltages, which can be attributed to the high electron density and rapid charge transport at the PTAA/perovskite interface.^{56,50} This was further evidenced by the lower leakage current with the PTAA, which is reflected as the lowest interfacial non-radiative recombination (Figure 4c).⁵⁷

Figure 4: The applied bias-dependent (a) charge recombination resistance and (b) charge lifetime extracted from Bode plots, and (c) dark $J-V$ characteristics for the inverted PSCs with different HTLs.

We studied temperature dependence capacitance versus frequency ($C-f$) measurements in a range of temperatures from 298.15 - 368.15 K (Figure 6). The $C-f$ graph display three distinct regions at low frequency (LF), intermediate frequency (IF), and high frequency (HF). The high-frequency capacitance is attributed to the result of the series resistance imposed by the contact electrodes. The capacitance produced in the mid-frequency range corresponds to the dielectric relaxation in the perovskite layer and is expressed by the geometrical capacitance^{58,29} per unit area ($C_g = \frac{\epsilon \epsilon_0}{L}$). The constant value of capacitance, which is temperature-independent at the IF region suggests the stable geometrical capacitance associated with the perovskite layer. A significantly thermally-activated capacitance is observed, toward the low frequencies region. As a matter of fact, with a decrease in frequency, the capacitance first increases and subsequently drops rapidly to below zero with a negative value of capacitance in a PSC. The LF region is related to the ionic migration and interfacial charge accumulation at the perovskite/contacts interface.⁵⁹ We noted that the onset frequency (f_d) of the negative capacitance increases and shifts towards intermediate frequencies with increasing temperature, suggesting an increase in electrons recombination in defect states with temperature. With a temperature rise, ions start to migrate faster and leave behind the trap states. The shift in drop frequency with temperature is attributed to faster recombination of charge carriers in defect states created by ionic migration (Figure 5).

Figure 5: The device architecture used in this study and cartoon representing the mechanistic inside.

The PSCs with PTAA showed relatively lower f_d values as compared to other HTLs, suggesting lower charge carrier recombination at the perovskite/PTAA interface (Table S2). Moreover, Figure S7 illustrates the low variation of the temperature-dependent capacitance at intermediate and high frequencies. The PSCs fabricated with PTAA gave lower capacitance suggesting lesser charge carrier build-up at the interface. We ascribed this to the high carrier mobility of PTAA and aligned energy levels with perovskite. These findings are in agreement with the EIS studies.

Figure 6: Capacitance versus frequency at different temperatures of the inverted PSCs with, (a) PEDOT:PSS, (b) P3HT, and (c) PTAA.

3. Conclusions

We investigated the impact of hole selective layers in an inverted (*p-i-n*) configuration-based perovskite solar cells using three different polymeric materials (PEDOT:PSS, P3HT, and PTAA). The perovskite solar cells fabricated with pristine PTAA measured photovoltaic

performance with a PCE of 17.84% compared to PEDOT:PSS and P3HT of 14.07%, 15.20% respectively without the employment of any dopant. We unravel a mechanistic insight for the understanding of the charge dynamics behavior in perovskites solar cells and elucidated the presence of a chemical inductor loop, which produces a negative value within the low-frequencies range. The nature of interfacial contacts is an influential factor in defining charge recombination at the interfaces. Admittance spectroscopy revealed that the recombination resistance is higher for PTAA than for PEDOT:PSS or P3HT, based solar cells. Our investigation provides an approach for in-depth analysis and establishes a generic framework to grasp the inductive behavior of capacitance at low frequencies and its correlation to the interface contacts in terms of non-radiative losses.

4. Experimental

4.1. Materials

Chlorobenzene (CB, 99%), isopropanol (IPA, 99.9%), anhydrous dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, 99.8%), and *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.8%), 1,2-Dichlorobenzene (DCB) were purchased from Acros Organics. The chemicals for perovskite were purchased from Dyesol except for PbI_2 and CsI_2 which were obtained from Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI). PTAA ($M_n = 5000$ -15000 by GPC) and PEDOT:PSS (Clevios P VP.A1 4083) were procured from Xi'an Polymer Light Technology Corp and Heraeus Deutschland GmbH & Co, respectively. PCBM > 99.5% and Bathocuproine (BCP) were purchased from Solenne BV and TCI, respectively.

4.2 Thin-film and Device Characterization:

UV-vis spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 50) was employed to measure absorption spectra. We measured the surface microstructure using field emission scanning electron microscopy (Hitachi S-4800). The current density-voltage (*J-V*) studies were measured under irradiation of 1000 W m^{-2} (AM1.5, 1 sun) provided by an Oriel AAA solar simulator (Newport). The

generated photocurrent was recorded at a scan rate of 100 mVs^{-1} (pre sweep delay: 10 s) using Keithley 2400 source meter and 0.09 cm^2 black metal mask as the active area of the devices. The external quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra were recorded using a 150 W Xenon lamp attached to a Bentham PVE300 motorized 1/4 m monochromator. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were carried out using BioLogic SP-300 Potentiostat using a perturbation of 20 mV, over the frequency range from 2 MHz to 1 mHz, at room temperature. The capacitance-frequency measurements at different temperatures were performed via a Keysight precision LCR meter (model E4980A) along with a Linkam (LTS420) heating control system.

4.3. Device Fabrication

FTO-coated glass substrates were used by cleaning through ultrasonication with Hellmanex solution, deionized water, acetone, and isopropanol for 20 min each step sequentially. The cleaned substrates were then dried using compressed air. Subsequently, the cleaned substrates were subject to UV-Ozone treatment for 20 min and then transported to the argon purged glove box. Firstly, the specific HTL was deposited, PEDOT:PSS (spin-coated at 5000 rpm for the 30s followed by annealing at $140 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 min), P3HT (3 mg/mL in DCB, spin-coated at 5000 rpm for 30s followed by annealing at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min), and PTAA (1.5 mg/mL in Toluene, spin-coated at 6000 rpm for 30s followed by annealing at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min) separately. Before depositing the perovskite layer, 60 μL of DMSO was dropped on the PTAA layer. Triple cation perovskite $[\text{Cs}_{0.1}(\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{MA}_{0.1})_{0.9}\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.9}\text{Br}_{0.1})_3]$ was deposited according to our previous reports.²⁹ In the case of PTAA based solar cells, 60 μL of DMSO was dropped on the PTAA layer just before the perovskite deposition. The PC₆₀BM thin film as an electron transport layer was spin-coated (15 mg/mL in CB) at 1200 rpm for 30 s over the perovskite active layer. A thin layer of BCP (0.5 mg/mL in IPA) was deposited atop PCBM by spin coating at 5000 rpm

for 40 s followed by evaporating Ag (100 nm, $<1 \text{ \AA s}^{-1}$) in a thermal evaporator under low-vacuum conditions (10^{-6} Torr).

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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